

Marine Bioprospecting Landscape

Deliverable report

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1. Executive Summary

Marine bioprospecting, the exploration of ocean biodiversity for valuable compounds, is predominantly centred in Europe, Northern America, Australia and some Asian countries, such as Japan, South Korea and China. These regions boast advanced research institutions and funding opportunities that foster innovation in biotechnology and pharmaceuticals. In Europe, research infrastructures like EU-OPENSREEN (European Research Infrastructure for Chemical Biology and early Drug discovery), EMBC (European Marine Biological Resource Centre), ELIXIR (Research Infrastructure for life-science information) and the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) promote collaboration among scientists in the field of marine bioprospecting. Northern America benefits from a strong ecosystem of universities and biotech companies, driving significant advancements in the field. Meanwhile, the unique marine environments in Asia and Australia offer a rich source of untapped biological resources, making these regions key players in global marine bioprospecting efforts. This landscape analysis is based on expert consultations, published scientific articles and institutional websites.

2. Marine bioprospecting landscape analysis

2.1. Background / Introduction

Marine bioprospecting involves the systematic exploration of the marine environment to discover unique genes, chemical compounds, and organisms that may offer societal benefits or hold commercial potential. Despite the vast biodiversity of the oceans and the promising economic opportunities it presents, much of this resource remains untapped. Industries such as pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, electronics, and food are particularly interested in marine compounds that could lead to the development of new, innovative products. About 30,000 compounds of marine origin have been identified until today, and over 1,000 new compounds are identified annually, indicating a promising future for marine bioprospecting. Marine organisms, which are known for their ability to survive in complex and extreme environments, are a rich resource for natural marine products with antiviral, antibacterial, anticancer and anti-inflammatory properties. There is a diversity of groups spread around Europe and the world working on marine bioprospecting but efforts are fragmented across the European Research Area (ERA), and standardization and access to advanced biodiscovery-related services is often missing.

The EUREMAP project steps into a gap in the marine biodiscovery domain and aims to optimise Europe's marine bioprospecting pipeline, leveraging the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) EU-OPENSREEN (<https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>), EMBRC (<https://www.embrc.eu/>), ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/>) and EMBL-EBI (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>) with their affiliated expert groups. The integration of these expert groups across these RIs will enhance the competitiveness in marine natural products discovery for drug development and bolster the blue bioeconomy. EUREMAP is establishing a comprehensive pipeline of relevant services across these RIs to support other scientists to discover novel marine natural products. The project thereby strengthens the capacity of European RIs and facilitates the collaboration across academia and industry in the multidisciplinary field of marine biotechnology.

2.2. Description of work

The biodiversity of marine ecosystems, and hence chemical diversity of natural products, in different climate zones varies significantly. The EUREMAP consortium is spread across a diversity of European countries from the cold North (Tromsø in Norway) to the Atlantic (Faro in Portugal) and warm Mediterranean (Naples in Italy) connecting diverse institutions with access to a diversity of unique biological and technical resources, and socioeconomic ecosystems. EUREMAP seeks to establish strong links with relevant stakeholders and ensure the integration and interconnectedness of EUREMAP with relevant national and international initiatives.

To this end, we conducted a landscape analysis to identify international peers (including outside of Europe) who may be interested in collaborating with EUREMAP partners in the field of marine bioprospecting, facilitating the exchange of best practices, exchange of experiences with emerging technologies, harmonisation of operational standards at an international level, and exchange of data, samples and procedures.

2.3. Methodology

We conducted a literature review by using databases like PubMed and Google Scholar to search for recent papers, reviews, and studies on geographical trends associated with scientific publications describing new marine natural products and the geographic origin of these marine natural products. We used keywords specific to these questions, e.g., "marine natural products", "marine bioprospecting", "origin", "geographical trends", "region". The most relevant studies are quoted in the main text of this report and listed under chapter 3 (References).

We further identified leading research groups, institutions, universities and organisations by searching for the relevant scientific papers and reviews published over the last 15 years. The author lists and their affiliations indicate key players in the field and provided insights into research groups that worked on similar topics. We also looked into larger funded project consortia to identify researchers and groups with similar interests.

Furthermore, we analysed the conference programmes and speaker lists of important international conferences with a focus on marine bioprospecting. These conferences include the Gordon Research Conference (GRC) on Marine Natural Products, Gordon Research Conference on Natural Products and Bioactive Compounds, European Congress on Marine Natural Products (ECMNP), and International Symposium on Marine Natural Products (MaNaPro).

Scientific societies are also an important source of information for this landscape analysis. For example, the American Society of Pharmacognosy (ASP) created a map (<http://www.pharmacognosy.us/natural-product-programs-and-research/>), which is available on its website, with natural product investigators and programmes worldwide.

Finally, we consulted the EUREMAP consortium partners. These groups cover a wide range of relevant aspects of marine bioprospecting and have an excellent understanding of the research landscape. They are collaborating with numerous research groups worldwide, sometimes as part of larger EU consortia (e.g., MARBLES, BlueRemediomics), training networks (e.g., HOTBIO) or distributed, multinational research infrastructures (e.g., EU-OPENSREEN, EMBRC, ELIXIR).

The authors visited the websites of the identified groups to extract information on the research interests and aims of these research groups. This information, together with the website links, was included in tables 1-7.

Tables 1-7 list many research groups, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting. We decided not to include research groups that are working on plant natural products.

2.4. Results and Discussion

A recent study by Leal et al. applied several publication and authorship metrics for peer-reviewed marine bioprospecting publications reporting new marine natural products over the past 50 years (1965-2015) to evaluate which countries worldwide contributed the most to the scientific literature. An important finding was that scientists from only three countries (the United States, Japan, and China) co-authored half of all publications in the field. Among the ten most prolific countries are several European countries (Italy, Germany, Spain, France). Other non-European countries in the Top 10 are Australia, South Korea, and India. The most developed, high-income countries (besides China) have also the largest share in both regular and lead authorships. Furthermore, the authors of this study observed an increase in the number of countries that contribute publications on marine natural products, as well as an overall increase in the total number of annual publications. These numbers show that the capacity for marine bioprospecting is increasing globally.

From a geographical perspective, another important aspect is the geographic origin of the new marine natural products. The majority of new marine natural products, which have been discovered over the last decades, originated from marine invertebrates. Among these marine natural products from invertebrates, the vast majority were discovered in Asian countries (70%), followed by Oceania (Ref. Calado et al., 2022).

With the aim to add more granularity to the landscape analysis, individual research groups and initiatives worldwide were identified, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting. They are listed in Table 1-7. The scope of this analysis is on academic activities and Table 1-7 contains only a small number of companies. Though the tables are comprehensive and provide an extensive list of research groups and organisations, they do not claim to be exhaustive.

Table 1. List of multinational initiatives in Europe with a focus on marine bioprospecting:

European, multinational initiatives
<p>EU-OPENSREEN, Berlin, Germany</p> <p><i>Research:</i> A European research infrastructure for chemical biology and early drug discovery with partner sites in multiple countries. Partner sites with experience in marine bioprospecting, bioassay/bioprospecting, natural product extraction and purification, high-throughput compound screening, structure elucidation, natural products (semi-)synthesis, medicinal chemistry and hit-to-lead optimization, compound management, FAIR data.</p>

Website: www.eu-openscreen.eu

EMBRC, Paris, France

Research: A European research infrastructure for marine biology with nodes in multiple European countries. Local nodes with experience in marine bioprospecting, genome mining, bioassay/bioprospecting, natural product extraction and purification, structure elucidation, bioinformatics and data management.

Website: <https://www.embrc.eu/>

EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), Hinxton, UK

Research: Provision of bioinformatics resources and tools to the scientific community at large through its management of a unique set of key biomolecular databases. EMBL-EBI is one of twenty-three ELIXIR nodes and its databases are an integral part of the ELIXIR infrastructure and service delivery plan. One of those databases, MGnify, facilitates the assembly, analysis, and archiving of microbiome derived sequence data (>475K analyses) derived from a wide range of environments, and provides access to scalable analyses pipelines, and comprehensive metagenome assembled genome (MAG) collections.

Website: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/teams/microbiome-informatics/>,
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>

ELIXIR, Hinxton, UK

Research: European research infrastructure which brings together life science resources from across Europe, including databases, software tools, training materials, cloud storage and supercomputers. ELIXIR coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe so that researchers can more easily find, analyse and share data, exchange expertise, and implement best practices.

Website: <https://elixir-europe.org/>

EURMEAP

Research: EUREMAP is an EU-funded initiative which brings together four European research infrastructures with complementary fields of activity from discovering new compounds to screening their applications, while ensuring the resulting data are usable by the entire scientific community. EUREMAP aims to create a pipeline of research services in marine bioprospecting to support and enable the discovery of novel bioactive natural products from marine organisms. This pipeline will comprise a wide range of services spanning the biodiscovery process, from isolating specific molecules to testing their applications in clinical trials.

Website: <https://euremap.eu/>

MARBLES

Research: Horizon 2020 project (5-years), multinational (European) consortium. Development of new methods for the sustainable collection and use of biological resources from marine environments and assess their commercial potential.

Website: <https://marblesproject.eu/>

SECRETed

Research: Horizon 2020 project which develops novel molecules with tailor-made properties by the combination of biosynthetic genes of amphiphilic compounds (biosurfactants and siderophores) produced by marine and extremophilic microorganisms.

Website: <https://www.secreted.eu/>

BlueRemediomics

Research: Horizon Europe project which develops novel tools and approaches to explore marine microbiome data, uniting an international consortium of experts that will work on the discovery and production of high value sustainable marine microbiome-based products, processes and services

Website: <https://blueremediomics.eu/>

Algae4IBD

Research: Horizon 2020 project which studies under- and unexplored algae to look for compounds with pain-relieving, anti-inflammatory, prebiotic, or antibiotic effects

Website: <https://algae4ibd.eu/>

HOTBIO

Research: A Horizon 2020 Marie-Sklodowska Curie Action (MSCA) Doctoral Network Training project focusing on marine biodiscovery where secondary metabolites from marine microorganisms are developed into well-characterised compounds that can be applied as medicines, agrochemicals or aquaculture drugs.

Website: <https://www.hotbio.eu/>

SUBMARINER Network

Research: SUBMARINER Network (Sustainable Use of Baltic MARINE Resources). Cooperation platform for actors and initiatives across the Baltic Sea Region. Promoting innovative approaches for the sustainable use of marine resources. Partners: <https://submariner-network.eu/network-members/>

Website: <https://www.submariner-network.eu>

Table 2. List of European research groups and companies, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

Europe
<p>Sergey Zotchev, Division of Pharmacognosy, University of Vienna, Josef-Holaubek-Platz 2, Vienna, Austria</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Biologically active natural products from microorganisms; Genetics and biochemistry of natural product biosynthesis; Bacterial genomics; Metabolic engineering and synthetic biology</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://pharmakognosie.univie.ac.at/people/zotchev-sergey-b/</p>
<p>Blue Growth Research Lab, University of Gent, Belgium</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Blue Growth Research Lab at University of Gent focusses on valorisation and interaction with industry. Its research expertise includes bioactivity of marine molecules and bioassays for toxicity to environmental and human health.</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://bluegrowthlab.ugent.be/</p>
<p>Lone Gram, Center for Microbial Secondary Metabolites (CeMiSt), Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Unravel biological role of microbial secondary metabolites in natural microbiological communities.</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://cemist.dtu.dk/</p>
<p>Thomas Tørring, Aarhus University, Denmark</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Microbial biosynthesis, all aspects of these natural products. Identification of new natural products with pharmaceutical potential; by studying single enzyme encoded in biosynthetic gene cluster, we work towards a better understanding of how these natural products are constructed; through a chemical biology approach we attempt to identify their molecular target and mode-of-action; and importantly, we invest time in optimizing their production and aim for pilot scale production of the most promising compounds.</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://www.au.dk/en/thomast@bce.au.dk</p>
<p>Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Helsinki, Finland</p>

Research: Research organisation that builds sustainable future and well-being from renewable natural resources. Research also on natural products.

Website: <https://www.luke.fi/en>

Sorbonne University, Paris, France

Research: Sorbonne University, in cooperation with CNRS, is the main operator of EMRBC-France, which comprises the services and expertise of 3 marine stations: the Institut de la Mer de Villefranche (IMEV), the Observatoire Océanologique de Banyuls (OOB), the Station Biologique de Roscoff (SBR). Expertise in bioinformatics search for microorganism taxa possessing metabolic pathways for production of target secondary metabolites, identification, purification and structural characterisation of biomolecules of interest, development and implementation of new toxicological assay on marine organisms, screening to search for pharmacological inhibitors of protein kinases, valorisation

Website: <https://www.embrc.eu/embrc-network/france>

Clair Helio, Laboratoire de Biotechnologie et Chimie Marines, Centre de Recherche Saint Maudé, Université Européenne de Bretagne, Université de Bretagne-Sud, Lorient, France

Research: BIODIMAR's primary purpose is the valorization of bioactive natural substances of marine and terrestrial origin in the fields of health, cosmetology, nutraceuticals and biotechnology. BIODIMAR is a center of scientific expertise providing research services or collaborations for businesses and public research. The objective of the platform is to extract, purify and characterize marine biomolecules from its own collection (for example from marine organisms such as macroalgae, etc.), but also from private collections of marine organisms from atypical environments to which the platform has access thanks to exclusive partnerships. BIODIMAR supplies, either to academic research laboratories or to industry (pharmaceutical, cosmetics, blue or green chemistry or even agri-food), fractions or pure molecules from marine organisms and presenting original biological activity.

Website: <https://www.univ-brest.fr/biodimar/>

Mehdi Beniddir, Université Paris-Saclay, Paris, France

Research: Streamlined discovery and structure elucidation of intricate natural substances from plants, marine invertebrates and micro-organisms using MS-based dereplication approaches

Website: <https://www.biocis.universite-paris-saclay.fr/?Associate-Professor-of-natural>

Olivier Grovel & Catherine Roullier, University of Nantes, France

Research: Isolation, structure and evaluation of marine substances for pharmacological and therapeutic purposes; marine microorganisms; marine fungi; mass spectrometry; metabolomics

Website: <https://www.univ-nantes.fr/catherine-roullier>

Soizic Prado, Molécules de Communication et Adaptation des Micro-organismes (MCAM), Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France

Research: CPNFB Chemistry of Fungal and Bacterial Natural Products. The interactions of micro-organisms with other micro-organisms or with plants involve chemical communication mediated by small molecules. Natural substance chemistry and chemical ecology provide a molecular approach to these phenomena. The aim of our activity is to study the chemical nature (complexity, diversity), biological origin and role of the secondary metabolites (the "natural products") involved in these interactions, from gene to molecule and from their isolation to their chemical and biological synthesis.

Website: <https://mcam.mnhn.fr/en/cpnfb-chemistry-fungal-and-bacterial-natural-products-449>

Yanyan Li, Molécules de Communication et Adaptation des Micro-organismes (MCAM), Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France

Research: The team's activity focuses on the molecular aspects of defense and communication mechanisms as well as adaptive processes in prokaryotes in different environmental contexts.

Website: <https://mcam.mnhn.fr/en/bim-biochemistry-microbial-interactions-339>

Marie-Lise Bourguet-Kondracki, Molécules de Communication et Adaptation des Micro-organismes (MCAM), Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France

Research: Marine Natural Products, Antibacterials, Natural Product Chemistry, Structure Elucidation, NMR Structure Elucidation, Compound Isolation, Biological Activities, Antibacterial Activity, Antibiotic Resistance, Natural Product Drug Discovery, Metabolite Identification.

Website: <https://mcam.mnhn.fr/fr/annuaire/marie-lise-bourguet-kondracki-368>

ICSN Instiut de Chimie de Substances Naturelles, France

Research: Gathering a 200-collaborator staff, the ICSN is the chemistry center of the CNRS campus in Gif sur Yvette. The Institute belongs to the Paris-Saclay University Campus, which will incorporate 10% of the French research. The ICSN develops research activities at the boundary between chemistry and biology, that draw inspiration from natural substances. ICSN is organised in four research departments and has important analytical platform

Website: <https://icsn.cnrs.fr/en/research/sncm/marine-metabolites-isolation-synthesis-and-bioactivity>

Nathalie Bourgougnon, Marine Biotechnology and Chemistry Laboratory, University of Southern Brittany, Vannes, France

Research: Phycology; marine molecules; eco-friendly extraction processes; antiviral agents; SAR studies

Website: <https://www-lbcm.univ-ubs.fr/fr/le-laboratoire/qui-sommes-nous/membres.html>

Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (HZI), Braunschweig, Germany

Research: Discovery, optimization and translation of novel antiinfectives. Microbial natural products are a key resource for lead discovery. Expertise and capabilities in extraction and extract characterization using mass spectrometry-based untargeted metabolomics, structure elucidation by NMR, bioprofiling against diverse pathogens, as well as natural product (semi)synthesis.

Website: <https://www.helmholtz-hzi.de/>

Deniz Tasdemir, Marine Natural Products Chemistry, GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research, Kiel, Germany

Research: Focus on marine resources (macro- and micro-organisms) and their secondary metabolites (also known as specialized metabolites). Our first major research line (marine biodiscovery/biotechnology) explores the potential of such 'designer molecules' for discovery of new, bioactive molecules relevant for human health (e.g., as drug candidates), or for applications as agrochemicals, nutraceuticals or cosmeceuticals.

Website: <https://www.geomar.de/en/research/fb3/fb3-mn/research-topics>

Nadine Ziemert, University of Tübingen, Germany

Research: Translational natural product genomics, development of bioinformatic tools for the discovery of new antibiotics

Website: <https://www.medizin.uni-tuebingen.de/de/das-klinikum/mitarbeiter/profil/2113>

Brötz-Oesterhelt, University of Tübingen, Germany

Research: Molecular mechanisms of new antibiotic lead structures and operation modes of novel antibiotic targets.

Website: <https://uni-tuebingen.de/fakultaeten/mathematisch-naturwissenschaftliche-fakultaet/fachbereiche/interfakultaere-einrichtungen/imit/arbeitsgruppen/mikrobielle-wirkstoffe/ag-broetz-oesterhelt/>

Peter Schupp, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Germany

Research: Marine Natural Products in Environmental Context

Website: <https://uol.de/peter-schupp>

Nikolas Fokialakis, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Research: Discovery of bioactive metabolites from plants, terrestrial and marine microorganisms with anti-aging activities. The molecules discovered so far have applications in cosmetic and food supplements industry.

Website: <https://en.pharm.uoa.gr/>

Vassilios Roussis and Fay Ioannou, Section of Pharmacognosy and Chemistry of Natural Products, Department of Pharmacy, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Research: Isolation and structure elucidation of bioactive secondary metabolites from marine organisms.

Investigation of chemical communication and chemical defense systems of organisms. Application of natural polymers for the development nanomaterials for biomedical applications.

Website:

https://en.pharm.uoa.gr/people/faculty/pharmacognosy_chemistry_of_natural_products/roussis_vassilios/

Alan Dobson, Environmental Microbial Genomics (EMG), University College Cork, Ireland

Research: Research interests are the study of microorganisms in either natural or artificial environments and their potential biotechnological exploitation. Focus on gaining a fuller understanding of how microbes survive, grow and interact in their various ecological niches; an approach which is fundamental to their exploitation for biotechnological applications.

Website: <http://publish.ucc.ie/researchprofiles/D021/adobson>

Olivier Thomas (University of Galway), Ireland

Research: Our research focuses on the specialized metabolites, also called natural products, produced by marine organisms and especially marine invertebrates like sponges, zoantharians, soft corals but also algae, microalgae, or cyanobacteria. While our main playground for biodiscovery is the North-eastern Atlantic and especially the Irish waters from the seashore until the deep sea, through collaborations with local marine biologists and ecologists, we work in the Caribbean and Mediterranean Seas or the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans.

Website: <https://www.universityofgalway.ie/our-research/people/biological-chemical-sciences/olivierthomas/>; www.imbd.ie

Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN), Naples, Italy

Research: Ecosustainable marine biotechnology department is focused on the exploitation of marine sources aimed at the discovery of novel bioactive compounds as biosurfactants, antibiofilm, antimicrobials, anticancer, antioxidants and anthelmintic.

Website: <https://www.szn.it/index.php/en/>

CNR Institute of Biomolecular Chemistry (ICB-CNR), Naples, Italy

Research: Focus on bio-organic chemistry and chemical biology fields, with expertise and infrastructures in chromatography, NMR and MS analysis, spectroscopy, organic synthesis, extraction and fractionation of natural products by automated platforms, chemistry-guided isolation, structural elucidation and (semi)-synthesis of small organic molecules.

Website: <https://www.icb.cnr.it/en/>

Marialuisa Menna, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Naples, Italy

Research: Natural products chemistry; NMR spectroscopy; small molecules structure elucidation; bioactive marine metabolites; synthetic and medicinal chemistry; chemical libraries; marine-inspired leads to drugs.

Website: <https://en.unimib.it/paolo-galli>

NAICONS SRL, Saronno, Italy

Research: NAICONS is a biotechnology company specialised in the discovery of novel bioactive molecules from microbial sources. It relies on a large and diversified collection of 45,000 actinomycetes. micro4all platform.

Website: <https://naicons.com/>

Marine Research and Higher Education Center (MaRHE Centre), Bicocca University, Milan, Italy

Research: Biodiversity and Marine Ecology

Website: <https://marhe.unimib.it/about-marhe/team/>

Francesca Zanoni, SPHERA encapsulation, Dossobuono, Italy

Research: Italian company specialised in micro- and nano-encapsulation.

Website: www.sphaencapsulation.com

Cristina Varese, University of Turin

Research: Bioprospecting from marine fungi

Website: <https://www.dbios.unito.it/do/docenti.pl/Alias?giovanna.varese#tab-profilo>

Gilles van Wezel, Universiteit Leiden (ULEI), The Netherlands

Research: ULEI investigates "Fundamentals of Science", "Translational Drug Discovery and Development", "Bioscience: the science base of health", and "Health, Prevention, and the Human Life Cycle".

Website: <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/staffmembers/gilles-van-wezel/publications#tab-2>

Marnix Medema & Justin Van der Hooft, Wageningen University & Research, The Netherlands

Research: Develops innovative computational approaches to identify novel natural product biosynthetic pathways and connect them to specific molecules and phenotypes.

Website: <https://www.wur.nl/en/persons/marnix-medema.htm> <https://vdhooftcompmet.github.io/>

UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø, Norway

Research: Marbio is an analytical platform for screening, isolation and identification of bioactive natural products and has an extensive portfolio of projects including extracts from plants, animals and microorganisms collected from marine, freshwater and terrestrial environments. The main focus is to explore Arctic and sub-Arctic marine organisms, searching for compounds with activities against cancer, bacteria and diabetes as well as compounds with immunomodulatory and antioxidative effects.

Website: https://en.uit.no/forskning/forskningsgrupper/gruppe?p_document_id=380005

SINTEF, Trondheim, Norway

Research: Department of Biotechnology and nanomedicine with experience and projects in drug discovery and bioprocess engineering, as well as in vitro toxicology and safety assessment. Strong background in marine bioprospecting and large inhouse marine microbial strain collections as well as expertise in functional and molecular biodiscovery and in development of microbial production processes. SINTEF has state-of-the-art instrumentation for cultivation and bioprocess development, metabolomics and high-throughput and/or high content cell-based in vitro analyses.

Website: <https://www.sintef.no/en/expertise/sintef-industry/biotechnology-and-nanomedicine/marine-biotechnology-and-bioprospecting/>

Institute of Marine Research (IMR, Norway), Bergen, Norway

Research: IMR is one of Europe's largest marine research institutes, involved in sustainable exploitation of marine resources, including bioprospecting for new bioactive compounds from Norwegian marine ecosystems. It hosts Marbank, the national marine biobank of Norway, with a mission of providing academia and industry with easy and safe access to marine biological resources for research and exploitation purposes. Marbank holds samples and data of marine organisms collected in Arctic, sub-Arctic and boreal habitats, varying from the intertidal zone to the deep seas.

Website: <https://www.hi.no/en/hi/forskning/research-groups-1>

Patrycja Golińska, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Torun, Poland

Research: Research interests include Polyphasic taxonomy of actinomycetes from extreme and unexplored environments; Searching for bioactive filamentous actinomycetes from extreme biomes using a culture-based bioprospecting strategy and genome mining.

Website: https://www.bio.umk.pl/en/department-of-microbiology/staff/patrycja_golinska/

Anake Kijjoo, Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas de Abel Salazar and CIMAR Universidade do Porto, Portugal

Research: Antibacterial compounds from higher plants; marine invertebrates; soil and marine-derived fungi; cosmetic ingredients from marine resources; natural biopesticides

Website: <http://anakekijjoo.com/>

Ricardo Calado, Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies (CESAM), University of Aveiro, Portugal

Research: Marine Ecosystems & Resources, Principal Researcher and develops independent research on Sustainable Blue Growth, namely in the research fields of Applied Marine Ecology, Sustainable Aquaculture and Marine Biotechnology

Website: <https://www.cesam.ua.pt/ricardocalado/>

Maria do Rosário Domingues, Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies & Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Research: Mass spectrometry lipidomics; marine lipidomics; lipidomics in health and disease; food lipidomics; microbial lipidomics glycomics; biomolecules modification associated with oxidative stress monitored by mass spectrometry.

Website: <https://www.cesam.ua.pt/rosariodomingues/>

Centre of Marine Sciences (CCMAR), University of Algarve, Faro, Portugal.

Research: Marine plants; biotechnological applications; antioxidant activity; antioxidants bioactivity; phytochemicals; natural product chemistry.

Website: <https://ccmar.ualg.pt/>

João Carlos Serafim Varela, Centre of Marine Sciences, University of Algarve, 8005-139 Faro, Portugal.

Research: Microalgae; biofuels; marine bioactives; carotenoids; marine biotechnology.

Website: <https://ccmar.ualg.pt/users/jvarela>

Hugo Pereira (GM), Green CoLAB. HQ, Universidade do Algarve, Campus de Gambelas, Faro, Portugal

Research: Joining the pieces in Marine Algal research. Non-profit private organization, a collaborative platform between research and industry, whose research & innovation agenda is based on the exploration of macro- and microalgae as an essential component for different industries.

Website: <https://www.greencolab.com/>

Fundación MEDINA, Granada, Spain

Research: A non-profit research organization focused on the discovery of novel bioactive compounds from microbial natural products (NPs) to be developed as new drugs. Natural product research and drug discovery, with expertise in industrial microbiology and biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, NPs chemistry (isolation and structural elucidation), and HTS screening technologies. MEDINA's small molecule discovery activities focus on the screening of its unique microbial collection (190,000 strains of actinomycetes and fungi) and NPs libraries (200,000 extracts). Collaborative model engaging in contract research and collaboration programs with big pharma companies, biotech and academic centres.

Website: <https://www.medinadiscovery.com/>

PharmaMar, Madrid, Spain

Research: Pharmaceutical company specialized in the development of new anticancer drugs from marine natural products. They have a library with over 350.000 samples of marine organisms.

Website: <https://pharmamar.com/en/>

Manuel Salvador de Lara, IDENER, Seville, Spain

Research: Genome scale metabolic models for process optimization. Microbial community modelling.

Website: <https://idener.ai/>

Carlos Jiménez and Jaime Rodríguez, University of A Coruña, Spain

Research: Isolation and structural elucidation of natural products. Siderophores from pathogenic bacteria in fish. Chemical ecology. Synthesis of natural products and analogues. Applications of NMR in structural analysis.

Website: <https://www.pronamar.com/en/>

Ana R. Díaz-Marrero, Instituto de Productos Naturales y Agrobiología (IPNA), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Tenerife, Spain.

Research: Marine natural products; marine microbial compounds; bioassay-guided isolation; NMR structural analysis; biomedical applications.

Website: <https://www.ipna.csic.es/node/2479>

Javier Fernández, Instituto Universitario de Bio-Orgánica Antonio González (IUBOAG), Universidad de la Laguna (ULL), Spain

Research: Marine natural products; marine toxins; marine polyether; marine microalgae; biosynthesis; Laurencia; antiparasitic substances; phosphatase inhibitors.

Website: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jose-Fernandez-121>

Eva Nordberg Karlsson, Lund University, Sweden

Research: Research focus is on production, molecular development and enzymology of carbohydrate active enzymes from extremophiles and putative probiotic bacteria

Website: <https://www.biotek.lu.se/staff/professors/eva-nordberg-karlsson/>

Jörn Piel, Institute of Microbiology, ETH Zürich, Switzerland

Research: Investigates microbial natural products and biosynthetic pathways in underexplored microbes. Focus on discovering new bioactive compounds by studying the metabolic potential of microbial communities, including those in marine environment.

Website: <https://biol.ethz.ch/en/the-department/people/person-detail.MTKxNDA3.TGIzdC80NjAsOTIzMMDxMjly.html>

Shinichi Sunagawa, Institute of Microbiology, ETH Zürich, Switzerland

Research: Research areas include Global ocean microbiome, and Bioinformatic tools and resources

Website: <https://micro.biol.ethz.ch/research/sunagawa.html>

Marcel Jaspars, Marine Biodiscovery Centre, University of Aberdeen, UK

Research: Discovery of new compounds with potential pharmaceutical use from marine and desert environments, their structure determination and biosynthesis. Translation of bioactive natural compounds into preclinical evaluation is exemplified by with sponge derived compounds/analogues that have activity in animal models for Alzheimer's disease or epilepsy.

Website: <https://www.abdn.ac.uk/ncs/departments/chemistry/marine-biodiscovery-1280.php>

Katherine Duncan, University of Strathclyde, UK

Research: Marine microbial antibiotic discovery

Website: <http://www.medicinesfromthesea.com/>

RuAngelie Edrada-Ebel, Strathclyde Institute of Pharmacy and Biomedical Sciences, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK

Research: Marine natural products chemistry; secondary metabolomics; NMR- and MS-based metabolomics; marine biotechnology.

Website: <https://www.strath.ac.uk/staff/edradaebelruangeliedr/>

Eva Sonnenschein, Swansea University, UK

Research: Studies microbial interactions in marine microenvironments. Research focuses on microalgal holobiont (microalgae and their microbiome) and the plastisphere (microbial communities associated with marine microplastic). We employ molecular tools, high-throughput screening, -omics technologies and bioinformatics to understand the molecular mechanisms that form the basis for the ecological complexity of microbial communities. We ultimately aim to use this knowledge to identify novel, sustainable solutions for biotechnological applications.

Website: <https://www.swansea.ac.uk/bioscience/>; <https://www.sonnenscheinlab.com/>

Andrew W Truman, John Innes Centre, Norwich, UK

Research: Biosynthesis and function of bacterial specialised metabolites. A major focus of our research is the discovery and biosynthesis of RiPPs produced by Actinobacteria.

Website: <https://www.jic.ac.uk/people/andrew-truman/>

Zeller team, EMBL

Research: The lab develops computational tools, such as GECCO (used in EUREMAP genomic detection), for investigating how the microbiome influences human health, disease progression, and treatment. It focuses on analysing microbial genomes, metabolic pathways, and their interactions with environmental factors.

Website: <https://www.embl.org/groups/zeller/>

Table 3. List of research groups in Northern America, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

Northern America (Canada, USA)

Roger Linington, Simon Fraser University, Canada

Research: Technology development for chemical and biological characterization of natural products.

Website: <https://info.liningtonlab.org/>

Raymond Andersen, University of British Columbia Canada

Research: Isolation and structure elucidation of novel organic metabolites produced by marine organisms

Website: <https://www.chem.ubc.ca/raymond-andersen>

Ben Shen, Natural Products Discovery Center at University of Florida Scripps, USA

Research: UF Scripps houses one of the world's largest actinobacterial strain collections, totalling 125,127 strains. These strains were isolated over the last eight decades, with the majority acquired between 1940s to the 2010s. The wide time range of collection has allowed for capture of chemical diversity based on evolution and environmental cues, which change over time and are impossible to reproduce in laboratory settings today. Spanning at least 88 different genera, these strains were isolated from 69 different countries with different climate and ecology factors that further increase natural product structural diversity. The ~125K strains in the collection are estimated to produce more than 3.75 million natural products. In reference to the ~20,000 natural products that have been isolated from actinobacteria, the current number of known natural products is only ~1% of this value, leaving millions of compounds to be discovered. The strain collection therefore provides an unprecedented source of rich and unique natural product chemotypes to target emerging biology and accelerate drug discovery

Website: <https://shen.scripps.ufl.edu/natural-product-discovery-center-npdc/>

Amy Lane, University of North Florida, USA

Research: Research areas include chemical biology, drug discovery, marine natural products, natural product biosynthesis, organic chemistry and biochemistry

Website: <https://www.unf.edu/~amy.lane> (not working),

<https://loop.frontiersin.org/people/500561/overview>

Sandra Loesgen, University of Florida, USA

Research: Understanding the diversity and bioactivity of the chemicals produced by microorganisms, with an emphasis on compounds with medical applications. We employ a multi-disciplinary approach to isolate compounds produced by under-explored groups of microorganisms, and identify chemicals with anticancer, antibacterial, or antiviral activity.

Website: <https://loesgenlab.org/>

Jeffrey Rudolf, Department of Chemistry, University of Florida, USA

Research: We aim to discover novel bacterial natural products with biological activities by combining genomic information with methods of genetics, biosynthesis, and enzymology. We are particularly interested in bacterial terpenoids and the enzymes that create and oxidize these skeletons.

Website: <https://rudolflab.com/>

Hendrik Luesch, University of Florida, USA

Research: He leads a multidisciplinary marine natural products program with chemistry- and genomics-based discovery platforms that integrate classical isolation and spectroscopic structure determination, genome mining and synthetic biology, chemical synthesis, target identification, and mechanism of action as well as early development studies. He is founding Director of UF's Center for Natural Products, Drug Discovery and Development (CNP3).

Website: <https://pharmacy.ufl.edu/profile/luesch-hendrik/>

Bill J. Baker, University of South Florida, USA

Research: biodiscovery; cold-water chemistry; infectious disease drug discovery; marine invertebrates, fungi, algae; chemical ecology; biosynthesis; genome mining

Website: <https://eze500359.wixsite.com/bakerchemistry>

Amy Wright, Natural Products Chemistry Team, Florida Atlantic University, USA

Research: Focuses on the investigation of marine natural products with potential use as human therapeutic agents, as biological probes or as lead structures for medicinal chemistry. Our primary emphasis is on the discovery of compounds with anticancer properties, but we are also involved in collaborative research programs aimed at the discovery of agents useful against neurodegenerative disease and infectious diseases such as malaria and tuberculosis. Natural products are obtained from marine plants, invertebrates and microorganisms isolated from the tissues of marine invertebrates.

Website: <https://www.fau.edu/hboi/research/ocean-health-human-health/natural-products-chemistry/>

Wendy Strangman, Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of North Carolina Wilmington, USA

Research: Microbial natural products and pharmacokinetic evaluation of medicinal plants.

Website: <https://uncw.edu/chem/faculty/facstaff-strangman.html>

Joshua Pierce, North Carolina State University, USA

Research: Focus on harnessing the diverse architectures of marine natural products to inspire advances in chemical reaction development, synthetic design, chemical biology and therapeutic lead identification

Website: <https://piercgroup.wordpress.ncsu.edu/>

Andrea Bourdelais, Center for Marine Science, University of North Carolina at Wilmington, USA.

Research: isolation and structure elucidation of bioactive marine natural products; polyether compounds; bioassay screening; high content screening; quantitative analysis of marine toxins; harmful algal blooms; Florida red tide; marine dinoflagellates.

Website: <https://libres.uncg.edu/ir/uncg/clist.aspx?id=2485>

Julia Kubanek, Vinat Agarwal, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

Research: Investigation of chemical biology and ecology of marine natural products

Website: <https://kubanek.biosci.gatech.edu/>; <https://ocean.gatech.edu/research/ocean-technology>
<https://www.agarwallab.com/>

Andrew Lowell, Virginia Tech (Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University), USA

Research: Using chemical synthesis to elucidate natural product biosynthesis and biosynthetic enzymes as catalysts in chemical reactions.

Website: <https://chem.vt.edu/people/faculty/teaching-and-research/alowell.html>

Barry O'Keefe, National Cancer Institute, USA

Research: Expert in the screening of natural product extracts and the discovery of novel bioactive compounds. He has pioneered the discovery of biotherapeutics from natural products, especially in the area of antiviral proteins. He also specializes in the analysis and exploitation of protein-ligand interactions for both high-throughput screening and compound characterization. As Director of the Molecular Targets Program and Chief of the Natural Products Branch, Dr. O'Keefe is integral in the NCI's drug discovery efforts from natural product extracts.

Website: <https://ccr.cancer.gov/molecular-targets-program/barry-r-okeefe>;
<https://dtp.cancer.gov/organization/npb/staff.htm>

John Beutler, National Cancer Institute, USA

Research: Natural products isolation and structure elucidation, bioassay guided fractionation for cancer and antiviral activity, high throughput screening, sample libraries.

Website: <https://ccr.cancer.gov/staff-directory/john-a-beutler>

Lin Du, National Cancer Institute, USA

Research: Discovery and optimization of novel bioactive secondary metabolites from filamentous fungi and other natural sources.

Website: <https://ccr.cancer.gov/staff-directory/lin-du>

Kevin Tidgewell, Duquesne University of Kentucky, USA

Research: Medicinal and Natural Products Chemistry: Focus on natural products drug discovery and medicinal chemistry of CNS related diseases (pain, depression, anxiety) but we also have projects working on NTDs and cancer. We work with marine cyanobacteria from the Caribbean but also have collaborative projects on plant natural product analgesics from Cameroon.

Website: <https://thetidgelab.wordpress.com/>

Matt Bertin, Case Western Reserve University, Cleveland, Ohio, USA

Research: Isolation and structure characterization of marine natural products; algal toxin monitoring; secondary metabolite biosynthesis.

Website: <https://chemistry.case.edu/bertin-lab/>

David Rowley, University of Rhode Island, USA

Research: Microorganisms from unexplored environments; secondary metabolites produced by marine microbes; bacterial chemical communication; and antibiotic drug discovery.

Website: <https://web.uri.edu/pharmacy/research/rowley/>

Lesley-Ann Giddings, Smith College, USA

Research: Bioprospection of extreme environments for new antibiotics and characterizes enzymes involved in siderophore biosynthesis.

Website: <https://lgiddings.wixsite.com/giddingslab>

The Ohio State University, College of Pharmacy, Research in Drug Development & Discovery: Natural Products, USA: several research groups

Research: Several research groups in Drug Development & Discovery focussing on Natural Products: e.g., Kinghorn group, Fuchs lab, Rakotondraibe group, Carcache de Blanco group

Website: <https://pharmacy.osu.edu/research/natural-products>,
<https://microbiology.osu.edu/people/ju.109>, <https://u.osu.edu/fuchslab/>,
<https://u.osu.edu/rakotondraibe.1/>, <https://pharmacy.osu.edu/directory/esperanza-carcache-de-blanco>

Russell Hill, Institute of Marine and Environmental Technology (IMET), USA

Research: Diversity and roles of microbial symbionts associated with marine invertebrates, in particular sponges; Marine microbes, including symbionts of marine invertebrates, as sources of novel bioactive compounds with pharmaceutical potential; Marine microalgae for production of biofuels and other bioproducts; Marine molecular microbiology

Website: <https://imet.usmd.edu/directory/russell-hill>

Marcy Balunas, University of Michigan, USA

Research: Focus on interaction-driven molecule discovery from host-microbe symbioses. We seek a fundamental understanding of how the metabolome mediates host-microbiota interactions, aiming to discover novel bioactive metabolites involved in chemical communication between eukaryotic hosts, their bacterial associates, and pathogenic organisms. Host-microbe symbioses are becoming an increasingly important focus in biomedical research as the human microbiota is now recognized as a major contributor to health and disease.

Website: <https://medschool.umich.edu/profile/8870/marcy-j-balunas>,
<https://balunas.lab.medicine.umich.edu/>

Muraleedharan Nair, Michigan State University, USA

Research: All aspects of discovery, isolation, and identification of phytochemicals with potential as nutritional/functional food agents and phytomedicines to manage or treat diseases

Website: https://www.canr.msu.edu/people/dr_muraleedharan_nair

University of Illinois Chicago, USA: several research groups

Research: University of Illinois Chicago, College of Pharmacy with several research groups focussing on natural products, e.g., Molinski group (focus on Marine natural products), Orjala Laboratory (freshwater cyanobacteria), Eustaquio Lab, Murphy lab, Guido Pauli lab, Tadeusz Riley group

Website: https://www-chem.ucsd.edu/faculty/profiles/molinski_tadeusz_f.html,
<https://www.orjalalab.com/>, <https://eustaquio.lab.uic.edu/>, <https://www.murphylabuic.com/>,
<https://gfp.people.uic.edu/content/gfp.html>, <https://riley.lab.uic.edu/>

Northwestern University, USA: several groups

Research: Neil Kelleher: Microbial natural products. High resolution mass spectrometry to identify and evaluate novel secondary metabolites from bacteria and fungi. Jason Kwan: Kwan lab uses culture-independent (metagenomic) sequencing and molecular biology to understand how and why bioactive small molecules are produced by bacteria. Tim Bugni: Development of methods to mine the metabolomes of marine bacteria for new molecules. We study new molecules using mass spectrometry and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

Website: <https://www.kelleher.northwestern.edu/research/natural-products-discovery/#page-content>, <https://kwanlab.github.io/>, https://pharmacy.wisc.edu/faculty/bugni-research-group/?doing_wp_cron=1722332914.8755021095275878906250

Michael Smanski, University of Minnesota, USA

Research: Interface of synthetic biology and natural products biosynthesis.

Website: <https://www.smanskilab.tech/>

Christine Salomon, College of Pharmacy, Centre for Drug Design, University of Minnesota, USA

Research: Discovery of bioactive natural products and biological control organisms to treat infectious disease in humans, plants and animals. We collect and culture bacteria and fungi from subterranean caves and mines, terrestrial soils, plant endophytes, and aquatic environments. Current projects include the discovery of compounds and microbes to treat white nose syndrome in bats, soybean cyst nematode disease in crops, and biofilm-associated disease in humans.

Website: <https://drugdesign.umn.edu/our-faculty-staff/our-faculty/christine-salomon>

Cord Carter, Fisk University, Nashville, USA

Research: Marine Natural Products synthesis by using organic chemistry and microbiology.

Website: <https://www.fisk.edu/>

National Center for Natural Products Research, University of Mississippi, USA: several groups

Research: University of Mississippi with several research groups focussing on natural products, e.g., Stevens group, Chittiboyina group, Boudreau lab, Khan group

Website: <https://www.stevenslab.com/>, <https://www.boudreaulab.org/>,
<https://pharmacy.olemiss.edu/ncnpr/team/dr-ikhlas-a-khan/>

Jordan K. Zjawiony, Department of BioMolecular Sciences, School of Pharmacy, University of Mississippi, MS 38677, USA

Research: Marine biotechnology; pharmacognosy; natural products; semisynthesis; medicinal chemistry.

Website: <https://olemiss.edu/bms/>

Lukasz Ciesla, The University of Alabama, USA

Research: Plant specialized metabolites

Website: <https://bsc.ua.edu/people/lukas-ciesla/>

April Risinger, The University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio, USA

Research: Our pharmacology laboratory collaborates with natural product chemists to determine the mechanism of action and antitumor efficacy of compounds with anticancer potential.

Website: <https://lsom.uthscsa.edu/pharmacology/team-member/risinger-april-l/>

Robert Cichewicz, University of Oklahoma, USA

Research: Natural Products Discovery Group (NPDG) investigates biomolecules produced by fungi to understand their natural functions and discover ways these compounds can be translated into new medicines and valuable organic materials.

Website: <https://www.ou.edu/cas/chemistry/people/faculty/robert-cichewicz>

Vanessa Phelan, University of Colorado, USA

Research: Chemical ecology of environmental and host-derived microbiome communities

Website: <https://www.thephelanlab.com/>

Jaclyn Winter, University of Utah, USA

Research: Exploration of the biomolecular chemistry of natural products produced by microorganisms

Website: <https://www.bioscience.utah.edu/faculty/winter/index.php>

Katharine Watts, California Polytechnic State University, USA

Research: Focus on biosynthetic pathways in Actinobacteria.

Website: https://chemistry.calpoly.edu/content/faculty/watts_katharine

Katherine Maloney, Point Loma Nazarene University, USA

Research: Isolation and structure elucidation of natural products from endophytes that inhibit plant pathogens.

Website: <https://www.pointloma.edu/faculty/katherine-n-maloney-phd>

University of San Diego (UCSD), USA: several groups

Research: UCSD with several research groups focussing on natural products, e.g., Pieter Dorrestein group.

Website: <https://dorresteinlab.ucsd.edu/>, <https://pharmacy.ucsd.edu/faculty/moore>, <https://pharmacy.ucsd.edu/faculty/molinski>, <https://wgerwick.scrippsprofiles.ucsd.edu/>

Scripps Institution of Oceanography; UCSD, USA

Research: Natural Products Chemistry: Natural products chemistry is the study of substances produced by living organisms. Research can help improve the understanding of biological processes or identify compounds that may lead to the development of new drugs.

See also: Center for Marine Biotechnology and Biomedicine (CMBB) - Research programs focus on marine resources, from genes and molecules to organisms and ecosystems, that hold promise in the betterment of our wellbeing. CMBB scientists investigate a wide range of biotechnologies, from the special properties of deep-sea marine microbes to applications of transgenic “model” marine organisms.

Bradley Moore: Professor of marine chemical biology in the Center for Marine Biotechnology and Biomedicine at Scripps and a professor of pharmaceutical sciences in the Skaggs School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences at UCSD.

Paul Jensen: Research Interests: Microbial distributions and interactions with marine plants and invertebrates; Sequence-based approaches to the discovery of natural products from marine microbes; Comparative genomics; Microbial chemical ecology; Distributions, biogeography, and molecular evolution of marine bacteria.

Website: <https://scripps.ucsd.edu/research/topics/natural-products-chemistry>,
<https://scripps.ucsd.edu/cmhb>, <https://scripps.ucsd.edu/profiles/bsmoore>,
<https://pharmacy.ucsd.edu/faculty/moore>, <https://pjensen.scrippsprofiles.ucsd.edu/>

University of California, Santa Cruz, USA: several groups

Research: Several groups with interest in natural products, e.g., MacMillan lab focuses on the isolation and characterization of natural products from marine-derived bacteria that have promising biological activity.

Website: <https://macmillanlab.sites.ucsc.edu/>, <https://www.sanchezlab.science/>

Oregon State University, USA: several groups

Research: Several groups with interest in natural products, e.g., Benjamin Philmus group (cynobacteria), Taifo Mahmud group, Kerry McPhail lab

Website: <https://pharmacy.oregonstate.edu/users/taifo-mahmud>,
<https://pharmacy.oregonstate.edu/McPhailLab/>,
<https://pharmacy.oregonstate.edu/philmuslab>

Carole Bewley, NIH Natural Products Chemistry Section, Baylor University, USA

Research: Discovery and development of new classes of molecules that are effective in preventing infections by bacterial and viral pathogens with an emphasis on compounds effective against drug-resistant bacteria and enveloped viruses. Use of modern spectroscopic methods, including NMR, HR-MS and computation, to fully determine the structures of new natural products; genome sequencing to characterize their biosynthesis; and structural biology to gain an atomic view of how natural products are synthesized or exert their biological activities.

Website: <https://irp.nih.gov/pi/carole-bewley>, <https://www.niddk.nih.gov/research-funding/at-niddk/labs-branches/laboratory-bioorganic-chemistry/natural-products-chemistry-section/research>

Daniel Romo, Baylor University, USA

Research: Chemistry and Biology of natural products

Website: <https://www.danielromogroup.com/>,
<https://chemistry.artsandsciences.baylor.edu/person/daniel-romo-phd>

C. Benjamin Naman, San Diego Botanic Garden, USA

Research: Natural Products Drug Discovery with an Emphasis on Studying Medicinal Plants, some marine Cyanobacteria, and Other Algae

Website: <https://www.namanlab.com/naman-benjamin>

Shugeng Cao, Daniel K. Inouye College of Pharmacy, University of Hawaii at Hilo, USA

Research: Biologically active compounds from marine fungi, endophytic fungi from Hawaiian plants, terrestrial soil fungi from volcanic mountains, and other microorganisms; Active components and their biological effects of herbal medicines; small molecules and their functions in microorganisms, animals, and human beings.

Website: <https://pharmacy.uhh.hawaii.edu/research/cao-lab>

Philip Williams, University of Hawaii at Manoa, USA

Research: Discovery and evaluation of marine and terrestrial secondary metabolites as potential drug leads for the treatment of cancers and Alzheimer's Disease.

Website: <https://manoa.hawaii.edu/chem/groups/williams/>

Wenjun Zhang, College of Chemistry, UC Berkeley, USA

Research: Research theme includes understanding and engineering the biosynthesis of natural products, new bioactive small molecule discovery and functional study, and development of new research toolkit to promote the natural product research with a particular focus on natural product tagging and applications

Website: <https://chemistry.berkeley.edu/people/wenjun-zhang>

Daniel Udvary, Joint Genome Institute, USA

Research: Use and development of bioinformatics tools for elucidation of biosynthetic gene clusters in bacteria and fungi.

Website: <https://jgi.doe.gov/our-science/scientists-jgi/daniel-udvary-secondary-metabolites/>

Elizabeth I. (Betsy) Parkinson, Purdue University, USA

Research: Discovery of new NPs from cryptic biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) and the examination of the anticancer and antibiotic activities of these NPs with a focus on difficult-to-hit targets. Major research areas are: 1) Chemicals induction of cryptic BGCs for the discovery of novel bioactive NPs; 2) Synthesis of peptide macrocycles inspired by cryptic biosynthetic gene clusters; 3) High throughput assays for challenging anticancer and antibacterial targets

Website: <https://www.mcmp.purdue.edu/faculty/eparkins>

Eduardo Caro-Diaz, University of Puerto Rico, USA

Research: Medicinal Chemistry of Marine Natural Products: Translation of the secondary metabolism of marine organisms into new therapeutic leads applied to human health. This process includes isolation of new natural products from oceanic environments and development of these compounds through medicinal chemistry to optimize their pharmaceutical properties.

Website: <https://www.ecarolab.com/>

Alejandro M. Mayer, Midwestern University, USA

Research: Marine pharmaceuticals: marine natural products as pharmacological agents for the modulation of inflammatory and neurotoxic mediators generated by activated microglia.

Website: <https://facultyprofiles.midwestern.edu/107-alejandro-m-mayer/grants>

Allison Walker, Department of Chemistry, Vanderbilt University, USA

Research: One area of focus is developing machine learning tools to facilitate engineering and discovery of natural products. Current research is focused on: 1) Developing algorithms that predict natural product activity from the biosynthetic gene clusters that produce them; 2) Using machine learning to investigate regulation of natural product production; 3) Developing tools to guide the engineering of biosynthetic gene clusters to produce novel natural product-like molecules; 4) Developing machine learning tools to design natural product-like inhibitors of protein-protein interactions.

Website: <https://as.vanderbilt.edu/chemistry/bio/allison-walker/>

Table 4. List of research groups in Latin America, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

Latin America

Roberto GS Berlinck, Universidade de Sao Paulo, Brazil

Research: Discovery of new bioactive metabolites from marine invertebrates and microorganisms (fungi and bacteria) as antiparasitic agents, antimicrobials, anticancer and enzyme inhibitors. Microbial metabolites of interest have the biosynthesis investigated. Organic synthesis to optimize structures and properties of natural bioactive compounds in collaboration with synthetic chemists involves students in our group. We also optimize methods for dereplication and microbial production.

Website: <https://qosbioiqsc.blog/roberto-berlincks-research-group-1/>

Camila Manoel Crnkovic, Universidade de Sao Paulo (FCF-USP), Brazil

Research: Microbial NP Biotechnology. Natural product drug discovery from cyanobacteria using a combination of metabolomics, genomics, and biological assays (cytotoxicity, antimicrobial and antileishmanial activities).

Website: <https://www.labazul.science/home>

Tsvetelina Mandova Gilson, University of São Paulo (USO), School of Pharmaceutical Sciences of Ribeirão Preto, Faculty of Pharmacy/ Pharmacognosy Lab, Brazil

Research: Purification of Natural Products by Liquid/liquid chromatography (Centrifugal Partition Chromatography); Structural elucidation; Pharmacological & therapeutical action of compounds; Ethnobotany.

Website: n/a

Vanderlan da Silva Bolzani, Sao Paulo State University – UNESP, Brazil

Research: Natural products from Brazilian huge biodiversity. Using the last advances on analytical tools our goal is to find anticancer and antimalarial candidates. With a long-term project (INCT BioNat) on biodiscovery, modern strategies to identify promising hits have been identified and characterized. Further chemical synthesis, pharmacological valuation are the goals of reaching a potential drug candidate.

Website: <https://nubbe.iq.unesp.br/portal/>

Leticia Costa-Lotufo, Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas, University of Sao Paulo, Brazil

Research: Laboratory of Marine Natural Products Pharmacology. Focuses on a combination of marine natural product discovery with molecular and cellular biology to identify new anticancer leads. The experimental approach includes: 1. Target-oriented isolation of new leads using functional chromatography and mass spectrometry techniques; 2. Studies on the mechanisms of action of anticancer leads using immunoaffinity fluorescent (IAF) labeled analogs and confocal imaging system, flow cytometry, western blotting and cell transection techniques; 3. Omics studies of marine invertebrates including metabolomics, metagenomics and functional metagenomics; 4. Studies on the mechanism of action of isolated anticancer compounds; 5. In vivo anticancer studies using animal models

Website: <https://ww3.icb.usp.br/leticia-lotufo-2/>

Beatriz Cámara, Technical University Federico Santamaría, Chile

Research: Molecular and genetic characterization of bioactive compounds from marine actinomycetes

<p><i>Website:</i> https://www.magisterquimica.usm.cl/academico/beatriz-camara-herrera/</p>
<p>Mario Figueroa, Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Our research group focuses on the discovery, isolation, and structure elucidation of bioactive natural products from fungi and bacteria from unexplored sources of Mexico.</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://quimica.unam.mx/perfil/mario-alberto-figueroa-saldivar/</p>
<p>Marcelino Gutiérrez G., Republic of Panama</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Chemistry of natural products from marine invertebrates from Panama. Chemistry of natural products of microorganisms associated with marine (corals and sponges) and terrestrial (plants, ants and amphibians) symbiotic systems</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://indicasat.org.pa/dr-marcelino-gutierrez/?lang=en</p>

Table 5. List of research groups in Asia, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

<p>Asia</p>
<p>Guangyi Fan, BGI, China</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Focuses on exploring global marine microbial diversity and its potential for biotechnological and biomedical applications. They recently published “Global marine microbial diversity and its potential in bioprospecting” https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-024-07891-2</p> <p><i>Website:</i> N/A</p>
<p>Yue-Wei Guo, Shanghai Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China.</p> <p><i>Research:</i> marine fauna and flora; chemistry and bioactivity of natural products; marine chemoecology; marine drug research.</p> <p><i>Website:</i> https://sciprofiles.com/profile/322007</p>
<p>Peiyuan QIAN, Department of Ocean Science and Division of Life Science, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology China</p> <p><i>Research:</i> Marine molecular ecology: Elucidating the complexity of microbial community dynamics (microbial molecular ecology) and chemical signals (marine natural products) of biofilms for larval settlement induction/inhibition and molecular mechanisms of larval response to chemical signals (larval omics). Also studying the molecular mechanisms of biological adaptation of marine animals in deep-sea and ocean trenches.</p>

Website: <https://life-sci.hkust.edu.hk/team/pei-yuan-qian/>

Hua-Shi Guan, Ocean University of China, China

Research: Marine drugs; marine natural products; marine glycotechnology; marine glycochemistry.

Website: <http://eweb.ouc.edu.cn/mp/tutorslistawz/list.htm>

Micha Ilan, Tel Aviv University, Israel

Research: Focus on two main areas: phylum Porifera (sponges) and its symbiosis especially with associated microorganisms (bacteria, Archaea & fungi) and macroorganisms (algae, invertebrates, fish & turtles). He studies sponge-derived natural products via marine biotechnology and chemical ecology, evaluating the potential of metabolites for pharmaceutical purposes, antifouling paints, etc. He also studies material sciences, especially biomineralization, their ecological/physiological function, and possible production of biomimetic materials.

Website: https://en-lifesci.tau.ac.il/profile/milan#anchor_research

Takaaki Kubota, Okayama University, Faculty of Medicine, Japan

Research: Isolation, structure elucidation, and biosynthetic studies of bioactive natural products from marine organisms, plants, and microorganism

Website: https://jglobal.jst.go.jp/en/detail?JGLOBAL_ID=200901006165468453

Nobuhiro Fusetani, Hakodate Research Center for Fisheries and Oceans, 20-5 Benten-cho, Hakodate, Japan

Research: Marine natural products; drug discovery; antitumor; antimicrobial; enzyme inhibitors; chemical ecology; biofouling.

Website: https://www.jst.go.jp/erato/en/research_area/completed/fck_P.html

Tamam El-Elimat, Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan

Research: Drug discovery from nature, particularly from fungi and plants, evaluation of the health benefits of medicinal plants and nutraceuticals and their chemical analysis, and pharmacokinetic herb-drug interactions.

Website: <https://www.just.edu.jo/eportfolio/Pages/default.aspx?email=telimat>

Dong Chan Oh (Seoul National University), Korea

Research: Metabologenomics-based logical natural product discovery. Structure elucidation of new natural products. Natural product chemical biology. Bioinformatic analysis of biosynthetic genes for natural products. Drug discovery based on microbial natural products.

Website: https://snupharm.snu.ac.kr/en/snu__professor/oh-dong-chan/

Hee Jae Shin, Marine Natural Products Chemistry Laboratory, Korea Institute of Ocean Science and Technology (KOIST), Busan, Korea

Research: Drug discovery and development from marine natural products. Natural Products from Marine Fungi

Website: <https://sciwatch.kiost.ac.kr/researcher-profile?ep=361>

Natural Products Research Institute, College of Pharmacy, Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea

Research: The institute consists of four research divisions: Natural Product Chemistry, Natural Products Resources, Biological Activity Research and Industrial Technology Cooperation.

Website: <https://snupharm.snu.ac.kr/en/natural-products-research-institute-2/>

Korean Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Incheon, Korea

Research: Exploration, discovery and commercializing of new bio-materials from polar organisms, specifically, pharmaceuticals such as antioxidants, dementia, cell protectant, anti-inflammatory drugs, antifreeze, and industrial application of cold-active enzymes.

Website: https://eng.kopri.re.kr/site/eng/html/rsch/020101.html?mode=V&mng_no=111

Korean Pasteur Institute, Seongnam, Korea

Research: Antimicrobial resistance lab focussing on the discovery of novel antimicrobial agents

Website: <https://www.ip-korea.org/research/labinfo.php?gb=ARL>

Korea Research Institute for Bioscience & Biotechnology

Research: Novel biomaterials from natural products

Website: <https://oak.kribb.re.kr/researcher-profile?ep=159&type=Article>

Munhyung Bae, Gachon University, Korea

Research: Microbial chemical biology for natural product development

Website: <https://munhyunglab.creatorlink.net/Research>

Se-Kwon Kim, Department of Marine Science & Convergence Engineering, Hanyang University, Gyeonggi-do 11558, Republic of Korea

Research: Marine natural products; marine biotechnology, marine algae; anti-oxidant; anti-HIV; Anti-cancer; anti-allergy; anti-inflammation; marine cosmeceuticals; nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals

Website: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=s_XUyFgAAAAJ&hl=fr&oi=ao

Muhammad Ajmal Shah, Government College University Faisalabad, Pakistan

Research: Green extraction and enrichment of bioactive compounds in natural products and their bioevaluation for metabolic and aging associated diseases such as diabetes, obesity, cancer, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases.

Website: <https://profiles.gcuf.edu.pk/profile/ajmalshah>

Lilibeth Salvador, Marine Pharmacognosy Laboratory, University of the Philippines

Research: Medicinal and Natural Products Chemistry, Biochemistry, Pharmacology

Website: <https://msi.upd.edu.ph/faculty/lilibeth-a-salvador-reyes/>

Chih-Chuang Liaw, National SunYet Sen University, Kaohsiung, Taiwan

Research: Natural product chemistry: Research on: (1) Exploring the Antimicrobial Natural Products from Marine Microbial Resources, (2) Clarification of Marine Microbial Natural Products with Heavy-Metal Chelating Activity, (3) Development of Anti-biofouling Agents from Marine Resources

Website: <https://mbr.nsysu.edu.tw/p/406-1260-27881,r3901.php?Lang=en>

Experimental Drug Development Centre, Singapore

Research: Experimental Drug Development Centre (EDDC) is a national platform for drug discovery and development formed from the integration of A*STAR drug discovery and development units, namely, the Experimental Therapeutics Centre (ETC), Drug, Discovery and Development (D3), and Experimental Biotherapeutics Centre (EBC)

Website: <https://www.eddc.sg/our-capabilities/>

Table 6. List of research groups in Oceania, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

Oceania

Ron Quinn & Miaomiao Liu, Griffith University, Australia

Research: Ronald J Quinn / Miaomiao Liu Lab. Research projects aim to decode how the metabolome and proteome, two of the most important classes of molecules in biology, interact at the molecular level. This will generate deeper insight into the function of metabolites (natural products) which have a central role in communication, intraspecies interactions and interactions with therapeutic targets. Expected outcomes from the project include new annotations of the metabolome-proteome interaction landscape, and a new mass spectrometry-based platform for unbiased and rapid discovery of natural product-based probes. These project aims to solve a key

problem in natural product discovery: the inability to elucidate their biological targets. Therapeutic areas of interest include tuberculosis, malaria, Parkinson's disease and SARS-CoV-2.

Website: <https://ronquinnlab.com/>

NatureBank, Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery, Australia

Research: GRIDD's NatureBank is a unique drug discovery platform based on natural product extracts and fractions that have been derived from Australian plants, fungi and marine invertebrates. These samples have been processed into two libraries (an 20,000 natural product extract library and a 112,000 natural product fraction library), which are ready for high-throughput screening against any disease. NatureBank also holds more than 30,000 archived biota samples.

Website: <https://www.griffith.edu.au/institute-drug-discovery/unique-resources/naturebank>

Rob Capon, The University of Queensland, Australia

Research: We study marine and microbial natural products, to inspire innovative solutions to important scientific, medical and societal challenges. Our research delivers new knowledge of the structure and properties of natural products; new molecular probes to better understand living systems; new leads for the treatment of infectious, inflammatory and neurodegenerative diseases, cancer and pain; new antiparasitics to safeguard animal health; and new approaches to protect crops and the environment.

Website: <https://imb.uq.edu.au/research-groups/capon>

Mark Butler, MSBChem Consulting & Queensland University, Australia

Research: MSBChem Consulting serves clients in the areas of natural product and analytical chemistry, antibiotics, herbal medicines, drug development, scientific writing and management

Website: <https://msbchem.com/>

Sylvia Urban, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Research: Dr Urban is the research leader and founder of the Marine and Terrestrial Natural Product (MATNAP) research group in the School of Science (Applied Chemistry and Environmental Science). The research scope of the group is to explore the biodiversity of Australian marine and terrestrial organisms (e.g., plants, fungi, sponges, algae, etc.) in the quest for new compounds for the purposes of drug discovery other applications. To expedite the process of discovery, various dereplication and chemical profiling strategies have become an important focus of the research.

Website: <https://www.rmit.edu.au/contact/staff-contacts/academic-staff/u/urban-professor-sylvia>

Wei Zhang (Director), Marine Bioproducts Cooperative Research Centre, Adelaide, Australia

Research: Marine Bioproducts, Australia's largest R&D hub dedicated to producing new and sustainable products from our marine environment. Marine Bioproducts is a not-for-profit

Cooperative Research Centre (CRC) bringing together more than 70 partners from academia and industry.

Website: <https://mbcrc.com/>

Hélène Taiana Darius, Laboratoire de recherches sur les biotoxines marines, Institut Louis Malardé, Tahiti, French Polynesia.

Research: Marine biotoxins; seafood poisoning; dinoflagellates; toxin production; toxin bioaccumulation in the trophic chain; cell-based assays; ligand-receptor binding assays; monitoring programs

Website: <https://www.ilm.pf/recherche/biotoxines-marines/>

Rob Keyzers, Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand

Research: Bioactives natural product discovery from marine organisms and traditional medicinal plants from around the South Pacific, mainly from New Zealand and the Kingdom of Tonga.

Website: <https://www.wgtn.ac.nz/scps/research/research-groups/natural-products>

Table 7. List of research groups in Africa, which are active in the field of marine bioprospecting:

Africa

Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM), University of the Western Cape, Cape Town, South Africa

Research: Novel Marine Drugs (Prof. Trindade, Dr. Anita Burger, Dr. Lonnie van Zyl)

Website: <http://imbm.co.za/research/>

3. Conclusions and next steps

The next steps will be to prioritize the most relevant and important potential research groups who may be interested in collaborating with EUREMAP partners. In consultation with these groups, the scope and objectives of the future collaboration need to be defined, for example, by clarifying which outcomes and services of EUREMAP are the most helpful and beneficial for these collaborators and what type of collaboration they are seeking (e.g., data sharing, collaborative marine bioprospecting projects, joint publications).

4. References

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- Fifty years of capacity building in the search for new marine natural products. Leal MC, Anaya-Rojas JM, Munro MHG, Blunt JW, Melian CJ, Calado R, Lürig MD. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2020 Sep 29;117(39):24165-24172. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2007610117. Epub 2020 Sep 14.
- Bioprospecting of marine invertebrates for new natural products - a chemical and zoogeographical perspective. Leal MC, Madeira C, Brandão CA, Puga J, Calado R. *Molecules*. 2012 Aug 16;17(8):9842-54. doi: 10.3390/molecules17089842.
- Trends in the discovery of new marine natural products from invertebrates over the last two decades--where and what are we bioprospecting? Leal MC, Puga J, Serôdio J, Gomes NC, Calado R. *PLoS One*. 2012;7(1):e30580. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0030580. Epub 2012 Jan 20.
- Website of the American Society of Pharmacognosy: <http://www.pharmacognosy.us/natural-product-programs-and-research/>